

EXCHANGE OF PHOSPHATES ADSORBED BY CLAYS FOR OTHER ANIONS

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Anion-exchange measurements have been carried out with particular reference to phosphate ions, partly because it is important as a plant nutrient and partly because it has the peculiar property of becoming unavailable or fixed under certain conditions by clays and clay minerals. Anion-exchange resins saturated with hydroxyl, oxalate, citrate and fluoride ions have been used for the exchange measurements. Hydroxyl, citrate and oxalate ions of the anionic resin exchange themselves for phosphate in varying extents, but fluoride is almost incapable of releasing phosphate under the conditions of the experiment.

It has been reported (Midgley, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1940, 5, 24; Sinha, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 415) that kaolinites and kaolinitic clays adsorb larger amounts of phosphates than montmorillonitic or other types of clays. The phosphate adsorption capacity (p.a.c.) of kaolinite can appreciably be increased by grinding the mineral alone or in presence of phosphates (Sieling, *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*, 1946, 11, 161). The reaction between phosphates and the kaolinitic clays may, under certain conditions, be so drastic that decomposition of kaolinite occurs in varying degrees. The major portion of phosphate adsorbed by kaolinite remains unavailable towards plants or extracting solutions. It is 'fixed', so to say. About the mechanism of 'fixation', no definite conclusions have yet been arrived at. It is, however, reported that added phosphates can be exchanged almost entirely for anions such as fluoride, citrate, oxalate and hydroxyl ions (Marshall, "The Colloid Chemistry of the Silicate Minerals"). Phosphate adsorption by clay minerals was earlier reported by Chatterjee and Dutta (*Indian J. Soil Sci.*, 1951, 2, 224).

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to measure the available phosphates by setting up an equilibrium exchange reaction between the adsorbed phosphates on the kaolinitic clays and the anion-exchange resins, saturated with anions like F^- , OH^- , citrate³⁻ and $C_2O_4^{2-}$, according to the technique of Brown and Albrecht (Res. Bull. No. 477, College of Agric., Univ. of Mo., 1950).

The advantage of using the exchanging anionic resin lies in the fact that exchange will take place against a known anion, quite unlike the soil, which is likely to contain more than one kind of anions. Since dissolution and complex formation (Haseman *et al.*, *Soil Sci.*, 1950, 70, 257) are eliminated in this way, the exchange behaviour of the process may otherwise be regarded as simulating plant-root-soil system and, hence, will measure strictly that part alone which is available by exchange.

EXPERIMENTAL

The electro dialysed clay fraction ($<0.5\mu$) of a sample of kaolinite from Rajmahal, Bihar State, was phosphatised by adding 0.1N- H_3PO_4 , adjusting the pH to 4.0 with NaOH solution and allowing several days for the reaction to proceed. The phosphat-

tised clay was then washed free of the excess of phosphate with double-distilled water, care being taken to prevent hydrolysis of the clay-phosphate complex by excessive washing. The p_H value of about 4% suspension, thus obtained in double-distilled water, varied between 5.5 and 6.0.

The total amount of phosphate adsorbed by the kaolinite clay (or p.a.c.) was then determined by estimating the amount of phosphate extracted by boiling with a solution of 1.0N-NaOH for 10 minutes. The soluble silicates were first removed from the filtrate by the usual method. The colorimetric method of Peech and English (*Soil Sci.*, 1944, 57, 169) was followed for the determination of phosphate, but instead of visual comparison, the colour was matched in the Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. The p.a.c. estimated in this way amounted to 17.8 m.e. PO_4^{3-} per 100 g. kaolinite.

The anion-exchange resin (Amberlite IR-410), supplied by Messrs. Rohm & Haas, was in the chloride form. From this the hydroxide, fluoride, oxalate and citrate forms were prepared by leaching with $M/5$ solutions of sodium hydroxide, fluoride, oxalate and citrate respectively till the leachate was free from chloride. After washing off the adhering ions, the resins were dried in an electric oven at 105° and kept in desiccators.

The anion-exchange capacity of the OH-resin was determined by treating it with an excess of standard acid and back-titrating the excess. The value so determined was 458 m.e./100 g., and was taken to be the same for the fluoride, citrate and oxalate resins.

Measurement of Exchangeable Phosphate.—The experimental procedure consisted in placing the phosphatised kaolinite suspension in a bottle and dipping into it a cellophane bag containing a known weight of slightly moistened anionic resin. The amounts of the phosphatised kaolinite as well as of the resin were varied. The amounts of resin, for instance, in each set of experiments were so taken that these corresponded to 1.0, 1.5, and 2.0 and 3.0 times the symmetry concentration.

After allowing the system to remain in this condition for 7 days, the bag containing the resin was taken out of the clay suspension. The amount of phosphate present in the clay after exchange was then determined by the method of Peech and English (*loc. cit.*). The phosphate so determined is expressed in m.e. of PO_4^{3-} ions per 100 g. of phosphatised kaolinite. The results are recorded in Tables I to IV.

TABLE I

*Reaction between OH-resin and phosphatised kaolinite.*Total $PO_4 = 17.8$ m.e., $p_H = 6.0$.

	Amount of resin corresponding to	M. e. of PO_4 -ion exchanged for OH-ions/100 g.		
		1.033% clay.	2.066% clay.	4.132% clay.
1.	1.0 S.	6.6	8.7	Nil
2.	1.5 S.	7.7	9.5	4.5
3.	2.0 S.	...	9.6	7.0
4.	3.0 S.	17.8	13.3	10.4

TABLE II

*Reaction between oxalate-resin and phosphatised kaolinite.*Total $\text{PO}_4 = 17.8$ m.e. $p_H = 6.0$.

Amount of resin corresponding to		M. e. of PO_4 -ions exchanged for oxalate-ions/100 g.		
		1.033% clay.	2.066% clay.	4.132% clay
1.	1.0 S.	1.7	2.2	Nil
2.	1.5 S.	2.4	2.2	Nil
3.	2.0 S.	3.2	2.5	Nil
4.	3.0 S.	5.2	2.5	1.8

TABLE III

*Reaction between citrate-resin and phosphatised kaolinite.*Total $\text{PO}_4 = 17.8$ m.e. $p_H = 6.0$.

Amount of resin corresponding to		M. e. of PO_4 -ions exchanged for citrate-ions/100 g.		
		1.033% clay.	2.066% clay.	4.132% clay.
1.	1.0 S.	10.9	3.3	3.6
2.	1.5 S.	11.9	7.7	6.1
3.	2.0 S.	15.7	9.9	10.8
4.	3.0 S.	17.8	13.6	10.8

TABLE IV

*Reaction between F-resin and phosphatised kaolinite.*Total $\text{PO}_4 = 17.8$ m.e. $p_H = 6.0$.

Amount of resin corresponding to		M. e. of PO_4 -ions exchanged for F^- -ions/100 g.		
		1.033% clay.	2.066% clay.	4.132% clay.
1.	1.0 S.	Nil	Nil	Nil
2.	1.5 S.	Nil	Nil	Nil
3.	2.0 S.	Nil	0.2	Nil
4.	3.0 S.	0.6	1.7	1.3

DISCUSSION

From the above data it is evident that extent of replacement of phosphate depends on the nature of the exchanging anion associated with the resin. Fluoride ions are apparently unable to replace phosphate from kaolinite (except a very small amount at high symmetry concentration) under the conditions of the experiment. It may be noted that a mixture of NH_4F and HCl at p_H 3.0 is capable of completely releasing adsorbed phosphate and this procedure is recommended for the determination of available phosphorus in soil (Bray, Bull. Ag. No. 1021, Agr. Expt. Sta., Illinois, 1942). The p_H of the phosphatised clay in the present experiment is about 6.0 and the high p_H may be responsible for the observed discrepancy.

Hydroxyl, oxalate and citrate ions, on the other hand, can replace varying amounts of phosphates from phosphatised kaolinite according to the respective capacity of each; the amounts of phosphate exchanged generally decrease to a small extent with the concentration of the phosphatised kaolinite. It appears that from 4% suspension, the oxalate ions are almost incapable of releasing the phosphate. In the case of concentrated clays, longer time is usually allowed for equilibrium.

Exchange of phosphate for the citrate ions increases with the quantity of citrate resin, i.e., symmetry concentration, but the amount of exchange decreases with increasing concentration of the suspension. It appears therefore that the availability of the phosphate ions is reduced as the clay becomes more and more concentrated. Activity measurements have similarly shown that the extractability or availability of cations is reduced at high concentrations of clay (Chatterjee, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 399) due possibly to the overlapping of double layers and consequent "immobilisation" of the ions in the double layer. A similar state of affairs may be envisaged in the case of phosphate availability.

FIG. 1

The three anion-exchange isotherms (Fig. 1), drawn for the least concentrated system, show their difference from the base-exchange isotherms, which are usually concave to the concentration.

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